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Digital Pipeline Linking Material, Engineering and Manufacturing Data

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Summary: European manufacturing requires a shift to adaptable, high-quality production, leveraging smart manufacturing and digital technologies to stay competitive amid rising product variety and shorter lifecycles. Smart manufacturing and mass customization, supported by digital pipelines, simulation-based twins, and data-driven intelligence, can address these needs, but SMEs still face barriers such as dependency on physical prototypes, modular production costs, and data management issues. This paper presents the development of an integrated and interoperable digital pipeline tool capable of aggregating and orchestrating data from product development and multidisciplinary modelling tools, materials properties and materials characterization, together with manufacturing and product quality assurance.

Keywords: Digital thread, Pipeline, AutomationML, Dataflow, File management.

1. Introduction

European manufacturing is undergoing a transformative phase, driven by intense global competition, increasing demand for product customization, and the need for shorter product lifecycles. Manufacturers are now required to produce smaller batches, often a single unit, to meet the growing trend of personalized products. This shift challenges traditional rigid production models, which are optimized for high-volume, low-variability output. In this dynamic environment, the ability to adapt quickly to changing customer demands while maintaining high product quality, cost efficiency, and shorter lead times has become a critical competitive advantage. To address these challenges, the industry is increasingly moving toward mass customization and smart manufacturing, leveraging advanced technologies to enable flexible, efficient, and responsive production systems [1, 2].

The key to this transformation is the integration of digital pipelines, simulation-based digital twins, and data-driven intelligence. These technologies facilitate high-mix/low-volume production by seamlessly linking materials, engineering, manufacturing, and quality data throughout the product lifecycle. By creating a unified digital thread, manufacturers can achieve real-time visibility and control over every stage of production, from initial design to post-lifecycle retirement. This holistic approach not only enhances operational efficiency but also supports continuous improvement through data-driven insights and predictive analytics [3, 4].

However, the adoption of these advanced technologies presents significant challenges, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). SMEs often face barriers such as the reliance

on physical prototypes for validation, the need for modular yet cost-intensive production systems, and the requirement for comprehensive materials knowledge and adaptive quality control mechanisms. Additionally, the volume and heterogeneity of the data generated across the product lifecycle can overload traditional data management systems. While cloud-based solutions have been proposed to address these issues, they often fall short due to limitations in cost, latency, and scalability, particularly for real-time applications in manufacturing environments [5, 6].

To overcome these challenges, novel product development strategies are needed to ensure and optimize the quality-, cost-, and time-efficient manufacturing of new products or variants in low-volume production systems. These strategies must emphasize multi-disciplinary and collaborative management of knowledge, enabling the seamless exchange of information across design, engineering, materials science, manufacturing, and quality assurance domains. Such an integrated approach requires the development of advanced digital tools capable of aggregating, orchestrating, and analyzing data from diverse sources, ensuring that all relevant information is accessible and actionable throughout the product lifecycle [7, 8].

This paper presents the development of an integrated and interoperable digital pipeline tool designed to address these needs. The tool aggregates and orchestrates data from product development and multidisciplinary modeling tools, materials properties and characterization, manufacturing processes, and product quality assurance. By linking product specifications, material properties, manufacturing data, and quality criteria, the tool ensures that all critical information is accessible and traceable from the initial design and conceptualization stages through

to production and post-lifecycle phases. This capability is essential for enabling real-time decision-making, reducing time-to-market, and ensuring consistent product quality [9]

The concept of a digital thread is central to this approach. A digital thread creates a continuous flow of information across all stages of the product lifecycle, including early concept development, design, manufacturing, operation, post-life, and retirement. This data-driven architecture relies on shared resources such as sensor outputs, computational tools, methods, and processes to enable both real-time and long-term decision-making [10, 11]. By tracing the evolution of components and products through the integration of Product, Process, and Resources (PPR) data [12], the digital thread provides a comprehensive framework for managing the complexity of modern manufacturing systems. Previous research has explored the use of AutomationML [13, 14], an XML-based object-oriented data modeling language, to link PPR data and support the continuous evolution of products and processes.

Building on this foundation, this paper introduces a practical implementation of the PPR model and presents a software tool (digital thread) capable of managing the diverse information generated throughout the product lifecycle. The tool is designed to address the specific needs of SMEs, providing a scalable and cost-effective solution for integrating digital technologies into their operations. By enabling seamless data sharing and collaboration across disciplines, the tool supports the transition to smart manufacturing and mass customization, helping manufacturers remain competitive in an increasingly complex and dynamic global market [15, 16].

2. Methodology

This section presents the steps and design choices to develop the proposed digital thread application.

2.1. Requirements

The initial phase of developing the digital thread application involves the identification of the core requirements to ensure the system meets its intended objectives. The primary requirements for the application are as follows:

- should provide an easy-to-use, user-friendly interface for defining dataflows. This includes drag-and-drop functionalities to enable users to create and modify dataflows seamlessly.
- must support the upload and download of various file types, including large files. This ensures flexibility in handling diverse data formats and sizes commonly encountered in production environments.
- should allow users to link files to specific production steps. This ensures traceability and context for each file within the production process.

- each production step should support the inclusion of metadata, such as the software used to generate a specific file. This enhances the ability to track and understand the context of data throughout the production lifecycle.

- must provide tools for visualizing the data collected within the dataflow. This enables users to analyze and interpret the data effectively, supporting decision-making processes.

- should be capable of exporting the defined dataflow as a hierarchical PPR (Product, Process, Resource) data model. The preferred format for this export is AutomationML, ensuring compatibility with industry standards.

- robust user management features, including authentication and authorization mechanisms, are required to control access to the application. This includes the ability to manage user roles, permissions, and grants to ensure data security and integrity.

2.2. Architecture

The system design is based on containerized microservices architecture, which provides flexibility, scalability, and ease of maintenance. This modular approach facilitates the addition of new functionalities and the efficient management of resources. The architecture is divided into four main responsibilities (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Digital Thread Architecture.

- The **Identity and Access Management (IAM)** system provides single sign-on (SSO) mechanism for all services within the system, allowing for centralized management of users and groups. Developing this system in-house has been avoided because widely used open-source alternatives offer long-term security and stability.

- The **digital thread information** is traced through RESTful architecture, where the relationships of the different components, as well as the permission system based on users and groups provided by IAM, are stored in a NoSQL database. This solution was selected due to the flexibility and high performance that NoSQL databases typically offer in read and write operations.

For sharing the digital thread with other systems, a service has been developed that transforms the system's internal data structure into the AutomationML format, ensuring interoperability between different tools and systems used in industrial automation.

- Similarly, for **file management**, a REST API is used, with which metadata and the permission system are stored in a NoSQL database. Additionally, binary data is stored in an S3 storage system, creating a datalake of unstructured data. This allows for a clear separation between metadata and file content, facilitating scalability and efficient resource management.

From the S3 storage, event-driven architecture is implemented, enabling asynchronous communication through events with the rest of the services. This architecture provides the system with great flexibility, scalability, and decoupling. Within this event-driven architecture, there are currently two main services: one responsible for confirming the correct upload of binary data to the system and another ETL (Extract, Transform, Load) service that structures the data of the main types of files used in industrial processes, such as hdf5, asc, aml, stl and mx3d. This process establishes a Data Warehouse that facilitates integration with other services that consume the data. One of the consuming services is the 3D viewer, which, thanks to the ETL process, provides a unified visualization of the different compatible formats.

- To facilitate the use of the entire system, a **web-based user interface** has been developed that integrates all these functionalities. This interface enhances usability when generating digital threads and provides a comprehensive overview of the various stages of the process. The web interface is designed to be intuitive and user-friendly, ensuring that users can easily navigate through the system's features.

2.3. PPR Model

The three fundamental components of production systems—Product, Process, and Resources (PPR)—are methodically arranged and optimized in manufacturing, engineering, and project management using the PPR model. This model ensures alignment between the product being produced, the processes required to manufacture it, and the resources necessary to execute those processes. By systematically addressing these components and their interdependencies, the PPR model provides a structured framework for achieving efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and quality in production. Industries such as automotive, aerospace, and industrial manufacturing have widely adopted this approach to streamline operations, enhance innovation, and maintain competitiveness in dynamic markets [17].

The *Product* component represents the final output or deliverable of a manufacturing system or project. It encompasses the design, specifications, materials, and quality standards required to achieve the desired

outcome. The product is characterized by its structural and functional properties, which are typically documented through detailed schematics, technical drawings, or a bill of materials (BoM). Understanding the product involves analyzing its components, their interconnections, and the performance and reliability criteria that define its success. This component serves as the foundation for subsequent processes and resource allocation, as it dictates the requirements for manufacturing and quality assurance [8].

In the context of the digital thread, the *Product* component is implemented through internal elements such as identification, bill of materials, and technical data. These internal elements capture essential information about the product, including its unique identifiers, constituent parts, and technical specifications. By digitizing this information, manufacturers can ensure traceability and accessibility throughout the product lifecycle, enabling real-time updates and seamless collaboration across teams. This digital representation allows for continuous monitoring and optimization, ensuring that the final product meets both design and market requirements [10].

The *Process* component refers to the systematic series of steps required to transform inputs into finished products. It includes stages such as design, prototyping, production, testing, and validation. The process is designed to maximize efficiency, minimize waste, and ensure consistency in the quality of the final product. Key considerations in process design include workflow optimization, process management, and the integration of feedback systems to identify and correct deviations or inefficiencies. By leveraging process optimization techniques, organizations can enhance productivity, reduce costs, and improve the repeatability of outcomes [17].

In the digital thread, the *Process* component is implemented in the final internal element, which outlines the steps and procedures taken to bring the product to its current state. This internal element captures the sequence of operations, their dependencies, and the criteria for transitioning between stages. For instance, in aerospace manufacturing, the *Process* component might detail the steps for assembling an aircraft engine, including machining, assembly, and quality inspection. By digitizing these processes, manufacturers can simulate and optimize workflows, identify bottlenecks, and ensure compliance with regulatory standards [8].

The *Resources* component encompasses the tools, equipment, personnel, and infrastructure required to execute processes effectively. This includes physical assets such as machinery and facilities, human resources with specialized skills, and intangible assets such as software, data, and energy. Effective resource management involves planning, allocating, and optimizing these assets to ensure their availability and efficient utilization. Proper resource management is critical for maintaining process continuity, achieving production targets, and delivering the desired product quality [10].

Within the digital thread, the *Resources* component is integrated into the *Process* internal element, where the resources required for each operation are specified. These resources are categorized as *Resources* element (e.g., equipment, physical and digital tools, personnel) and *Information* (e.g., design files, quality metrics, operational data). The interrelationship between resources and information is particularly important, as certain data may serve as inputs or outputs for other operations. By digitizing resource allocation and utilization, manufacturers can optimize capacity planning, reduce downtime, and ensure that all necessary assets are available when needed [17].

Fig. 2 shows the PPR model developed, providing a systematic framework for integrating product design, process planning, and resource management. By addressing each component and its interdependencies, manufacturers can achieve a harmonious balance of efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and quality. This balance is essential for driving innovation and

competitiveness in modern production systems. The digital thread concept builds on the PPR model by creating a continuous flow of information across all stages of the product lifecycle. This data-driven architecture enables real-time decision-making, enhances traceability, and supports continuous improvement [8].

In practice, the PPR model shapes the outcome of the digital thread application by ensuring that all relevant information is captured, linked, and accessible throughout the product lifecycle. This integration allows manufacturers to identify inefficiencies, predict potential issues, and implement corrective actions before they impact production. By leveraging the PPR model within the digital thread framework, manufacturers can transition from reactive to proactive management, ultimately enhancing their ability to meet customer demands and adapt to market changes [10].

Fig. 2. PPR Model using AutomationML.

3. Implementation

The Digital Thread is being implemented to provide and source of truth and interoperability across materials-modeling-manufacturing ecosystem [4] supporting the product evolution from the material characterization and design to the different manufacturing processes and quality assurance steps, furthermore, without losing sight of a general utilization for other value chains. The application was implemented in MX3D [18] use case in the scope of PIONEER project [19]. This use-case is defined by three pool lanes (Fig. 3). The first one deals with material characterization and the creation of different models (mechanical/metallurgical, thermodynamics and properties) that digitally characterize the material.

The second pool lane deals with engineering processes (topology optimization, Additive Manufacturing Design, CAPP, thermo-mechanical coupled models, and thermo-mechanical reduce order model) that use mechanical requirement and CAD boundary constraints. The third pool lane describes manufacturing and inspection operations. As can be seen from the above lines, the three pool lanes are interrelated, even more, due to the implementation of closed-loop controls to optimize the strategy and get the best product possible.

So, turning to the application, Product Owner (PO) created a Product Digital Thread Flow using Workflow Editor tool [20] describing product workflow that includes all operations mentioned in three pool lanes (Fig. 3). After that, PO added all product information

related to the three first internal elements of PPR Model (Fig. 2). All information provided for all different operations involved in product workflow was uploaded into the application through the Files Upload Tool. Metadata tags were also added to files to extend

information using Tag Button (actions column). These tags provide extra information external to the file and help to perform faster searches. To continue, for each operation, specific resources have been linked, providing more information to the digital thread.

Fig. 3. Product Workflow in the web application.

Also, some kind of files (.HDF5, .ASC, .AML, .STL and .MX3D) could be previewed using a preview tool [21] as shown in Fig. 4. Next step was to link operations with their information (operations' outcomes). Finally, the application's outcome was converted into an AutomationML format following a PPR scheme explained in the previous chapter. The Digital Thread outcome is a digital representation of the product across its lifecycle. These outcomes can be shared with other users through an interface that allows users to choose which other users and with which permissions a digital thread of a product is shared. This feature enables the collaboration of different organizations across the value chain.

Fig. 4. Preview in the web application.

4. Conclusions and Future Work

This application addresses the challenges outlined in the introduction by providing a robust solution for tracking static product lifecycle information across a wide range of industries. By leveraging a node-based

editor that links Product, Process, and Resources using the PPR model, the application ensures seamless integration and interoperability. The use of widely adopted standards such as AutomationML further enhances its compatibility with existing systems, making it accessible to organizations that already utilize PPR-based structures. AutomationML enables the representation of complex manufacturing data in a standardized way, facilitating collaboration and data sharing across different platforms and stakeholders.

The application is designed to be user-friendly and highly adaptable. Its node-based editor allows users to visually map and manage the relationships between products, processes, and resources, providing a clear and intuitive interface for creating and modifying digital threads. This capability is particularly valuable for industries that require high levels of customization, traceability, and efficiency in their production processes. While the application represents a significant step forward in digital thread technology, several challenges and opportunities lie ahead as the tool evolves to meet the demands of modern manufacturing.

One of the key challenges is the integration of the application with existing Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) and Manufacturing Execution Systems (MES). By enabling seamless data exchange with these systems, the application could automatically generate a digital thread for each product instance, reducing manual effort and improving accuracy. This integration would also allow for real-time updates and synchronization, ensuring that all stakeholders have access to the most current information.

As regulatory requirements evolve, there is a growing need for tools that support the creation

of Digital Product Passports (DPPs). A DPP provides a detailed digital representation of a product's lifecycle, including information on materials, manufacturing processes, and environmental impact. By integrating the application with upcoming DPP frameworks, manufacturers can ensure compliance with regulations while also enhancing transparency and sustainability.

To improve the efficiency of read/write operations on the various databases used by the application, the implementation of load balancers is essential. These technologies can distribute the workload across multiple servers, reducing latency and improving performance. Additionally, optimizing database queries and indexing strategies can further enhance the application's responsiveness, particularly when handling large volumes of data.

As the application gains adoption across different industries, scalability and adaptability will become increasingly important. The tool must be capable of handling diverse use cases, from small-batch custom manufacturing to large-scale mass production. This requires a flexible architecture that can be easily customized to meet the specific needs of different industries and organizations.

Future iterations of the application could incorporate advanced analytics and artificial intelligence (AI) capabilities to provide deeper insights into the product lifecycle. For instance, predictive analytics could be used to identify potential bottlenecks or quality issues before they occur, while machine learning algorithms could optimize resource allocation and process workflows. These capabilities would enable manufacturers to move from reactive to proactive management, further enhancing efficiency and competitiveness.

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